

INDUCTION HEATING OF THERMOSETTING CFRP MOLDS FOR COMMINGLED PP/GF COMPOSITE FORMING

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the development of an optimized coil pattern for uniform temperature distribution during induction heating of thermoplastic composite PP/GF using a thermoset CFRP mold. While CFRP molds offer advantages in lightweight structure and reduced heating and cooling times, they have limitations in achieving uniform heating due to anisotropy. To address this, various coil patterns were designed and analyzed for heating efficiency, resulting in a pattern capable of maintaining uniform temperature distribution even in complex geometries. The PP/GF composite produced using the optimized pattern is expected to achieve high quality without compromising mechanical properties, as compared to conventional molding methods. This research is anticipated to enhance the industrial feasibility of induction heating-based molding processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

Induction heating is a process that generates induced currents within a conductor through electromagnetic induction, thereby heating the conductor due to resistive losses [1, 2]. When a high-frequency alternating current flows through the coil of an induction heating device, a fluctuating magnetic field is created within the coil, forming a strong magnetic flux around it. When a conductor is placed within this magnetic field, eddy currents are generated within the conductor, flowing in a direction that opposes the change in the magnetic field, according to the law of electromagnetic induction [3]. The induced currents within the conductor produce Joule heating due to electrical resistance, resulting in rapid heating. This method of induction heating is known for its high energy efficiency, as it allows precise heating of specific regions, thereby reducing processing time [4]. Additionally, as the heating process is contactless, it does not damage the surface of the conductor. The skin effect due to high-frequency currents enables uniform temperature control in targeted areas, contributing to improved product quality [5]. Moreover, since no combustion is involved, induction heating provides a clean and safe working environment, making it a preferred heating method for mass production and automation, and an environmentally friendly solution [6].

Metal molds have traditionally been widely used in various manufacturing processes due to their high strength and thermal conductivity, but they have recently shown limitations in weight and thermal inefficiency [7]. Consequently, CFRP molds with lightweight properties and excellent thermal stability have emerged as an attractive alternative [8]. CFRP molds are lighter than metal molds and can be fabricated in thin layers, which shortens heating and cooling times and significantly reduces energy consumption [9]. Additionally, CFRP has a low coefficient of thermal expansion, which minimizes thermal deformation at high temperatures, making it suitable for precision processing, especially in

processes requiring repeated high-temperature heat treatments. Thus, CFRP molds offer a viable alternative to metal molds by addressing their limitations and proving effective in high-temperature processing applications.

Despite these advantages, CFRP molds present inherent challenges during the heating process due to their anisotropic nature [10]. The electrical and magnetic properties of CFRP vary according to the fiber orientation within the material, making it difficult to achieve uniform electromagnetic field distribution, which complicates even heating with standard coil arrangements [11]. Specifically, the induced currents generated by electromagnetic induction are often deflected or concentrated in certain directions within the CFRP, creating zones of interference where the currents cancel each other out. In these interference zones, heat transfer may be insufficient or overly concentrated, making it challenging to achieve a uniform temperature distribution across the entire mold [12]. This uneven temperature distribution can lead to inconsistencies in the quality and uniformity of processed products.

Therefore, this study aims to design a novel coil pattern that minimizes interference zones in the electromagnetic field and achieves more uniform heating by considering the anisotropic properties of CFRP molds. To accomplish this, various coil patterns were simulated, analyzing temperature distribution and magnetic field density to derive an optimal coil design. The developed pattern was successfully applied to uniformly heat CFRP molds. Subsequently, the heated CFRP mold was used to fabricate thermoplastic composites composed of commingled PP/GF, with plans to perform mechanical property tests on these composites. Through this approach, the study seeks to present an effective solution to the anisotropic challenges of CFRP molds, enhancing reliability and quality in thermoplastic composite molding processes.

2 MODELING AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Induction heating of the CFRP mold was numerically simulated to optimize coil placement. The CFRP model was a plate measuring $250 \times 300 \times 6 \text{ mm}^3$, with Litz wires comprising 1,500 strands of copper wire, each 0.12 mm in diameter. The working distance (WD) between the CFRP and the coil was set to 1 mm. The coil placement was tested in three configurations: a zigzag pattern (Figure 1a), a spiral pattern (Figure 1b), and a zig-spiral hybrid coil pattern (Figure 1c) newly developed in this study. In the zig-spiral hybrid coil pattern, adjacent coils were arranged with opposite current directions, and 180° turns were also oriented to maintain opposite current directions with neighboring coils. The spacing between coils was 20 mm, with a radius (R) of 20 mm for 90° turns and 10 mm for 180° turns. If the outermost coil (last coil) reached a higher temperature than preceding coils, uniform heating could be achieved by either decreasing the spacing from the previous coil or increasing the WD of the last coil. Additionally, to prevent excessive heating between the input and output of the coil, the spacing was minimized (approximately 0.5 mm) or eliminated altogether. The operating frequency and current were set to 152 kHz and 100.8 A, respectively.

Figure 1: Coil pattern geometries: (a) Zigzag, (b) Spiral, (c) Zig-spiral hybrid, (d) Curved-shape.

COMSOL Multiphysics V6.2 software (COMSOL, USA) was used to calculate the multiphysics of the electromagnetic field, electromagnetic induction, and heat transfer. Maxwell's equation was computed in the magnetic field interface, followed by heat transfer in the solid interface, to calculate Fourier's heat transfer law. A magnetic field interface was applied to the workpiece, induction coil, and air domain. Heat transfer in a solid interface was applied to the workpiece and coil domain. A heat flux boundary condition was added for convection in air, with a heat transfer coefficient of 10 W/m²·K.

Property	Parallel	Vertical
Electrical conductivity (S/m)	3.25×10^4	0.0325
Thermal conductivity (W/m·K)	2.4	0.59
Heat capacity (J/kg·K)	820	820
Density (kg/m ³)	1780	1780
Relative permeability	1	1
Relative permittivity	2156	1640

Table 1: This is the example of a table.

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Manufacturing of CFRP mold

The CFRP molds were fabricated using a high-temperature-resistant resin (LAS200M, KGF) and carbon-fiber fabric (Toray T300 plain-woven fabric, areal weight 200 g/m²) through an autoclave process. The resin was impregnated into the carbon-fiber fabric using the hand lay-up method, with 16 or 32 layers laminated on a mold of the desired shape. The resin-impregnated fabric was placed between release films and breathers, both above and below the mold, then wrapped in a nylon film and sealed under vacuum. Curing was performed at 175°C and 7 bar pressure in an autoclave for 2 hours, following the resin's curing conditions. After demolding, the mold underwent post-curing in an oven at 200°C for at least 2 hours. Three types of molds were fabricated: a 3 mm thick flat plate, a 6 mm thick flat plate, and a 3 mm thick plate with a 45° curvature.

Figure 2: Hand lay-up process (a) and vacuum bagging setup (b) for CFRP mold curing.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Optimization of coil pattern design

In the zigzag pattern (Figure 3a), the coil reached a high temperature of 404°C at the 180° bends due to the magnetic field reinforcement effect, resulting in a non-uniform temperature distribution. For the spiral pattern (Figure 3b), the center was heated to 58.8°C, while the pitch and coil sections in the cancellation zone reached 73.3°C and 89.6°C, respectively, and the linear coil section reached 106°C, indicating significant temperature variations across different sections. In contrast, the zig-spiral hybrid pattern (Figure 3c) exhibited a relatively uniform temperature distribution, with the center at 93.3°C, the pitch (between coils) at 108°C, the area directly above the coil at 145°C, and the last coil at 154°C, maintaining a difference of approximately 40-50°C. Temperature comparisons were illustrated in a graph after heating for 3600 seconds.

Figure 3: Temperature distribution for (a) zigzag, (b) spiral, (c) zig-spiral hybrid, (d) Curved-shape.

Figure 4: Temperature profiles: (a) spiral coil, (b) zig-spiral hybrid coil over 3600s heating.

5 CONCLUSIONS

An optimized zig-spiral hybrid coil pattern was proposed and validated for the induction heating of CFRP molds, addressing the challenge of uneven heating caused by the anisotropic properties of CFRP materials. Through simulation and experimental verification, the proposed design demonstrated significantly improved temperature uniformity compared to conventional zigzag and spiral configurations.

This improved uniformity is expected to reduce internal stresses, minimize defects, and enhance the quality of thermoplastic composite parts molded using CFRP tooling. The successful application of the coil pattern in heating CFRP molds and subsequent forming of commingled PP/GF composites confirms the feasibility of this approach for industrial use.

Furthermore, this study highlights the importance of coil design in electromagnetic heating applications and provides a scalable methodology that can be adapted for molds of various geometries and composite systems.

Future work will include mechanical testing of the molded composites to quantitatively evaluate property enhancement, and the development of closed-loop control systems for real-time heating uniformity monitoring. This research lays the groundwork for broader adoption of induction-based smart mold systems in high-performance thermoplastic composite manufacturing.

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